

METAMORPHOSIS OF AFRICAN ORAL TRADITIONS AND AESTHETICS IN THE RISE OF MODERN AFRICAN NOVEL

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Abstract

As a mirror that reflects an authentic African memory, African oral tradition as argued by Afrocentric scholars such as Chinwezu et al (1980) should be the point of departure for modern African literature. However, Eurocentric critics like Palmer (1979) posit that, elements of oral tradition in modern African fiction serve as mere embellishment and contrary to Afrocentric claim, does not contribute to the development of modern African fiction. This paper attempts to explore African oral tradition and aesthetics as employed by modern African writers in order to argue its role in the development of modern African fiction/literature. Selected literary works of writers in both colonial and postcolonial eras, are analyzed in order to examine the function of the African oral tradition and aesthetic in the selected texts. It is revealed that its role changes as the preoccupation and concerns of African writers shift. While most pioneer writers like Dennis Chukude Osadebay and Adali-Mortty, attempt to reach a compromise by directly translating African oral tradition in European languages, other writers such as Daniel Fagunwa, Okot p'Bitek and Ngugi wa Thiongo among others, attempted to adapt the oral into the written form, thereby creating a crossbreed between the two forms. In the contemporary era, African oral tradition and aesthetics is reconceptualised and reconfigured in order to capture African postcolonial reality as demonstrated by Kyuka Lilymjok in most of his literary works. Chinua Achebe and Wole Soyinka, on the other hand, exploited the oral tradition of their people by using it metaphorically in order to enhance the written form. Conclusively, translating, adapting and exploiting the oral form by modern African writers demonstrate that the African oral tradition and aesthetics is not limited to the role of embellishment as suggested by Palmer (1979) but rather, it continues to be a bedrock of modern African fiction, providing well defined outlook on African experiences.

Key words: oral tradition, African, Literature, aesthetics, modern African writers

Introduction

As a conduit through which the people's folklore is passed, preserved or manifests itself, African oral tradition and aesthetics such as proverbs, songs, oral performance, repetition, among others, have been employed by African writers to enhance their literary works for decades. While Afrocentric scholars such as Chinwezu et al (1980) posit modern African fiction should be rooted in the oral form, Eurocentric scholars believe African oral tradition and aesthetics employed by these writers do not impact the modern form due to their limited role of ornamentation in the texts. Thus, the intention of this paper is to examine the employment of African oral tradition and aesthetics by most African writers in various epochs in order to reveal whether it has an impact in the development of modern African fiction or if it is relegated to the role of embellishment. To achieve this, some selected works of some prominent writers in both colonial and postcolonial eras are analyzed in order to comprehend the function/purpose of oral tradition in these works.

It is a known fact that colonialism had a huge impact on African society, dismantling in some cases pre-existing structures. In an effort to justify the supremacy of western civilization over African culture, colonialists deliberately misinterpreted/misunderstood/misrepresented African culture and traditions. Words such as 'barbaric', 'primitive' and 'savage' were used to describe the culture. As a 'backward' culture, its folklore/indigenous knowledge system was underplayed. Due to its oral nature, African folklore was disregarded by foreign scholars who undermined the language and nature it was expressed, (Okpewho 1992). Drawing from this misconception, Eurocentric critics and scholars misinterpreted/misrepresented the African folklore.

This is demonstrated in their rather dismissive attitude when translating/interpreting folkloric elements or dressing these oral elements in European form so as to 'standardize' them for western intellectual consumption. For instance, Burton (1865) in his *Wits and Wisdom from West Africa*, commented on one of such disdainful prejudice against the African folklore common in his time. He explained that 'Poetry there is none...there is no metre, no rhythm, nothing that interests or soothes the feelings or arrests the passions,' (Burton 1865 in Okpewho 1992). Such claim is biased and projects prejudice against African oral traditions. It can be said that these oral traditions were deliberately misconstrued due to their inability to conform to Eurocentric literary aesthetics. For instance, an element of oral aesthetic such as repetition is used as a form of embellishment in European poetry, repetition in the African poetry/song is used for emphasis and enhances the oral performance. Thus, Eurocentric scholars such as Burton (1865) are said to deliberately analyze the African oral traditions via Eurocentric lenses and thus, their distorted understanding of the literature.

Drawing from such prejudice, contemporary critics of modern African literature employ the Eurocentric paradigm in their discussion of African literature/novel. Apart from advocating for the use of colonial languages as language of expression of the novel, they posit that the novel in Africa is a colonial import and as such, in terms of literary criticism, all novels must be judged uniformly. The contribution of African oral tradition in the development of the modern form, is underplayed. One of such Eurocentric critics is Palmer (1979) who argues that:

A number of African novelists incorporate elements of the oral tradition into their novels but these are not therefore an outgrowth of the oral tale. Much as we would like to think so for nationalistic and other reasons, the novel unlike poetry and drama is not an indigenous African genre. (Palmer 1979)

Relying on the use of African folklore as tool to label a novel African to Palmer (1979), is inadequate. The claim by Afrocentric writers such as Irele (1989) and Chinwezu et al (1980), among others that the African oral tradition contributes to the development of the novel in Africa is a myth to critics like Palmer (1979). He believes such Afrocentric claims are driven by a sense of nationalism and a tendency to reject everything associated with western colonialism/imperialism. While these contemporary Eurocentric critics agree literature exist in Africa, when it comes to literary criticism, these critics promote a formalistic rather than sociological approach. In other words, emphasis is laid on the quality of the intrinsic elements such as form and content at the expense of the extrinsic features like cultural and authorial background. This implies that, as cultural product, African oral tradition in modern African fiction is not considered relevant in the rise of novel in Africa, but as a mere means of ornamenting the language of a literary text.

However, despite these Eurocentric claims, when discussing the evolution of modern African fiction/literature, the influence of oral traditions cannot be ignored. Oral tradition continues to be an inexhaustible reservoir that modern African writers draw from, (Trinya 2015). As a response to the claim regarding the 'lack' of literature in Africa and subsequently, the dismissal of African oral traditions in strengthening the written form, modern African writers in both colonial and postcolonial eras seek to redefine the role of African oral traditions in the development of modern African novel/literature. In an effort to make the oral form more comprehensive to European audience, pioneer African writers (the apprentice) such as Dennis Osadebay, among others, directly translated certain oral songs and other elements. In most cases, their literary works though about the African experience/sensibilities, are dressed in European languages and aesthetics. This unfortunately only distorted the original content/function of the elements. In other words, it renders them un-African.

The second generation of writers such as Chinua Achebe and Wole Soyinka, among others, exploited the oral traditions of their culture in order to embellish their literary works. Okot p'Bitek, Ngugi wa Thiongo and some third generation writers such as Femi Osofisan and Kyuka Lilymjok, among others, adopted elements of African oral traditions in their works in order to prove its flexibility and adaptability. Since literature serves as a tool used to redefined the African culture/history that was deliberately distorted by Eurocentric scholars and critics such as Roper (1965), among others, the concept of translating, adapting and exploiting the oral reservoir by writers, indicates that, oral tradition has a pervasive infusion with the written form. Thus, the Eurocentric claims regarding the inadequacy of oral tradition in enhancing the written form in Africa, only demonstrates a prejudice against African indigenous knowledge system/folklore and culture in general by Eurocentricism.

If literature is a cultural product as argued by scholars such as Ngugi (1986), and folklore (oral traditions in this context) is regarded as the sum total of people's cultural heritage, wouldn't it be natural for the latter to influence the former? But then, if oral traditions can influence literature, how does it adapt and response to the various political shifts in the evolution of modern African fiction? Is it static or fluid/flexible in nature and adapts effortlessly to change? How does translating, adapting and exploiting elements of oral traditions by writers contribute toward affirming or debunking the Eurocentric notion that African oral tradition is limited to the role of embellishment and does not impact the development of modern African fiction?

African Oral Tradition: An Element of Embellishment or a Bedrock of Modern African Fiction?

In his effort to label the African novel an appendage to European novel, Roscoe (1971) argues that, the complexities of the novel could never be related by words of mouth. This suggests that, oral traditions even if they are sophisticated or not, are limited when it comes to the development of the novel. Roscoe's (1971) argument is similar to another Eurocentric critic; Obiechina (1975) who opined that African oral tradition does not impact the written form because 'literacy is crucial to the emergence of the novel, (Obiechina 1975: *Anthology of Criticism* 2007: p 325). That is, it is supposed to be read individually because the sustainability of the novel's complex narrative is more effective when read than when spoken.

Contrary to Roscoe (1971) and Obiechina (1975) arguments, there is evidence to prove that elements of oral traditions can enhance the development of modern literature in general. For example, epics, historically, around the world have demonstrated intricacies of plot, character, and theme, among others. For instance, in Europe, the epics of 'Beowulf', Virgil's 'Aeneid', and Homer's 'Iliad' and 'the

Odyssey,' among others contribute to the development of modern European fiction. Beowulf which is centered around subjects on heroism, battle between good and evil, transience and legacy, influences modern English writers today especially in the genres of adventure, fantasy and saga. These writers often employ motifs depicted in Beowulf such as the concept of mortality, courage, pursue of glory, essence of honor, among others.

One of such modern fictions that draws from the epic of Beowulf in terms of its tone, use of powerful imagery and motifs, is *The Hobbit* by John Ronald Reuel Tolkien and his other fantasy adventure- *The Lord of the Rings*. In these texts, the concept of Dragon-hoarding for example, is adapted from the epic of Beowulf which depicts Beowulf (the epic hero) fighting a dragon (his third encounter with a monster). Such oral narrative or epics contain some of the features of the modern novel and more importantly, deployed by modern writers to enhance modern fiction.

If literature is a 'cultural setting', then oral tradition and aesthetic is crucial in the formation of written literature in Africa. Critical works such as Namayi & Orina (2021) claim that African oral aesthetics such as tricksterism, humor and narrative technique enhances the language of the novel and resonates with the target audience. In addition, Chelule (2021) argues that these elements can be employed by writers to capture history and identity of a people as depicted in Khamisi's *Politics of Betrayal*; a memoir and his autobiography- *Dash before Dusk*. Rather than be used as tools for embellishment, Kurdi (2022) opines that oral elements such as proverbs for example, in a modern novel give more charisma to characters and give insight into the personalities of characters. This enhances the plot and sharpens the characterization, thus, giving the modern novel unique African identity. In novels like *Efuru* and *Idu*, by Flora Nwapa, folkloric elements such as myth fulfils a vital role of cultural interpretation and accounts for the history, realities and traditions of a people, (Asika 2011). This demonstrates that myth has a significant function in the development and execution of plot. In other words, without the inclusion of myth in a story like *Efuru* for instance, the text would have taken a different direction. Therefore, contrary to Palmer (1979)'s view that the only purpose of oral tradition in modern African novel is that of embellishment, is limited. Both African writers and critical works such as the ones above, have demonstrated that, while the African oral tradition can beautify and Africanize a literary work, it can contribute to the enhancement of the modern form.

Influence of African Folklore in the Development of Modern African Novel in Colonial and Postcolonial Eras

Several scholars such as Dundes (1965) and Bronner (2007) among others, argue that folklore (oral tradition in this context) is flexible and adaptive in nature. In

other words, as people evolve, so is their collective memory. As such, to effectively comprehend the contribution of African oral tradition in the development of modern African novel, it is imperative to explore its role/function in various epochs/periods in the development of modern African literature in order to depict its metamorphoses over the years in capturing the African experience.

African Oral Tradition in Precolonial Era

During the precolonial period, literature in Africa was generally based on oral transmission. Oral elements such as folktales, fables, parables, alongside other oral traditional elements were used not only for entertainment purpose but most importantly, to serve a didactic function. For instance, folktales in various cultures were used mostly for educational purposes. Children and adults knew about ethics and conduct, morality, wisdom, among others from the folktales in their culture. Legend on the other hand, inspires people (especially adults) to be the heroes of their time. This is because in precolonial African society, the hero according to Okpewho in his *The Epic in Africa*, quoted in Ojaide (2015), represents:

The highest ideal to which society can aspire. The hero is a good citizen who has leadership qualities and has a passion for justice, fairness, and a sense of pride in the homeland. (Okpewho 1992: Ojaide 2015)

Examples of oral traditions such as the *Epic of Sundiata*, *Ozidi* and *Mwindo*, encourage qualities like patriotism, courage, justice, patience, among others. Folktales such as *The Ajakpa Tales* (Yoruba), *Gizo da Koki*, among the Hausas, and the story of Anansi the Spider, among the Asante people of Ghana, promote a sense of belonging or communalism among people (Africans) and helps maintain a harmonious relationship with nature. Individualism in these stories is often depicted as a punishment (to people/individuals who deviate from their communal responsibility). Individuals whether young or old have a role to play in preserving the spirit of communal cohesion. It can be said that, African folklore in the precolonial era propagates the spirit of *Ubuntu* or as John Mbiti says of the African stand on individual, 'I am because we are' as opposes to Descartes's 'I am because I can,' (Mbiti 1969: Ojaide 2015).

Colonial Period

During colonial rule in Africa, western letters were introduced to new Christian converts to enable them to read and write the Bible. With such exposure, some of these converts began writing. Apart from translating the Bible into African languages, these writers borrowed the western letters to document the oral traditions of their people. The main purpose of including the oral folklore into the written form during this period, was to give identity to African literature. For

instance, Daniel O. Fagunwa in 1938 wrote the first novel in Yoruba, translated into English by Soyinka in 1962 as *A Forest of Thousand Demons*. The success of the novel relies heavily on the author's ability to explore elements of oral tradition to depict the adventure of Akara-Ogun in a forest infested with evil spirits. His novels generally, are laden with folktale traditions, myths, Yoruba cosmology and supernatural elements. Another important novelist using this style is Amos Tutola. In 1952, he published his *The Palm wine Drunkard*, which became the first novel to be published in English. Like Fagunwa, the novelist draws inspiration from Yoruba folktales, myths and legends to create a narrative that is similar to prose epic.

Fagunwa, Tutola and his contemporaries were more concerned with giving African literature a unique identity, thus, their heavy reliance on African folkloric elements to construct a novel. Fagunwa claims that:

Our duty is to present to our readers what we know will interest them. We should not merely copy others but should give first consideration to the need of our society...there is nothing wrong in making our own kind of writing our special contribution to the literary history of the world.
(Fagunwa 1960: Lindfors 1979)

Thus, despite being an educated man from one of the most prestigious colleges at that time (St Andrew's College), instead of embracing the English language and aesthetics in his writing, as was common among the apprentice writers of his generation, Fagunwa chose to represent his culture/folklore; to preserve it in literature. His work- *A Forest of a Thousand Daemons* published in 1939, apart from using the Yoruba language, relies heavily on Yoruba oral tradition and aesthetics to narrate the adventure of Akara Ogun. He successfully weaves together African oral tradition with the modern form to create a crossbreed between the two forms. For instance, at the beginning of the text, an African oral aesthetic is employed to begin the narrative. It begins in the first paragraph as:

'...the story which follows is a veritable *agidigbo*: it is I who will drum it, and you the wise heads who will interpret,' (*A Forest of a Thousand Demons* 1). This serves as a call to the audience/listeners to be active participants rather than passive (as expected in modern novel). It is a way of engaging the audience in the making and narration of the story. Similarly, in the second segment the narrator becomes the listener, through illustrative tales, he is taught on how to be moral. This depicts one of the elements of African folktale, which generally, has a didactic function.

Due to Fagunwa's novel reliance on African folklore/aesthetics, even after Soyinka's translation of the text into English, it is still able to maintain most of its Africanness. This is because African oral tradition and folklore in general

employed in the text is not restricted to the role of ornamentation but serves a didactic function.

African oral tradition and aesthetics continues to contribute to the development of modern African novel even in post Second World War era. Writers not only used the written form to document or give the oral form a cultural identity but in West Africa, the novel was used as a tool to write back to Eurocentric scholars and critics such as Roscoe (1971) and Povey (1972), among others, who disregarded the existence of an authentic African novel and most importantly, to debunk the claim made by earlier European scholars such as Roper (1965) that Africa lacked civilization prior to colonial rule. African oral tradition and aesthetics were heavily imported into the modern novel to prove in Achebe's word that:

African people did not hear of culture for the first time from Europeans; that their societies were not mindless but frequently had a philosophy of great depth and value and beauty, that they had poetry and, above all, dignity. (Achebe1975)

However, despite claiming that African people have their unique philosophy, poetry and aesthetic in the precolonial era, African modernist writers such as Soyinka, Christopher Okibgbo, and Achebe, fail in effectively capturing the authentic African identity in their literary works. This is because, rather than demonstrate African oral tradition and aesthetics' ability to change so as to fit in the present, they restricted its role to that of an ornamentation, thus, justifying Palmer (1979) claim that oral tradition and aesthetics is limited to the role of embellishment in the modern novel.

Achebe for instance, claims his famous work; *Things Fall Apart* is a novel written to prove to Eurocentric scholars and critics that Africa is a continent endowed with a rich cultural heritage/civilization which was distorted/destroyed by colonialism. He depicts the Igbo society at the dawn of colonial rule in Africa. Okonkwo who is the protagonist is portrayed as a man steeped in tradition, a successful man in terms of wealth, family and social status. On a sharp contrast, he is a rigid (resistant to change), proud and arrogant man whose life is turned upside down with the coming of Christianity and subsequently, colonial government in his community. His fear of being subsumed under foreign laws leads him to commit suicide (a taboo in Igbo land). In an effort to 'write back' to the West about Africa's glorious past, the author borrows excessively from the oral tradition of Igbo culture to prove his point.

However, a close reading of the text reveals that apart from serving as ornamentations, all the oral tradition such as the proverbs, myth, folktales and festivals among others, don't have any other function. Like Soyinka's *Idanre*, this novel only employs the oral form in order to make it look African. Most

importantly, the novel is said to prove the existence of civilization in the precolonial era but ironically, Western aesthetics - Aristotelian tragedy is employed to depict the tragic fall of Okonkwo and African culture in general. Aristotle states that a tragic hero as a man from noble background, high ranking status and possesses a flaw in character such as pride, fear, anger, as exhibited by Okonkwo, he also commits mistake (hamartia) which eventually leads to his downfall. In Okonkwo's case, the killing of Ikemefuna is the first mistake which dragged him down. Rather than show the adaptability of African oral tradition and aesthetics, the author adopts western aesthetics at the detriment of his people's oral tradition to explain Okonkwo's plight.

In East Africa, the application and function of oral tradition in the modern novel was quite different. Rather than exploit folkloric elements of their people, writers such as p'Bitek and Ngugi 'adapt' these elements to prove that African oral tradition is not static, but can adapt to change. Instead of writing back to the West regarding the existence of a glorious past in precolonial Africa, p'Bitek in *Africa's Cultural Revolution* claims it is the responsibility of the writer/storyteller to 'interpret and present Africa in their own way, in their own interests,' (p'Bitek 1973: Helda 2008). This means that, literary works should be in African languages and for African audience. In the words of Isidore Okpewho, p'Bitek had a firm attachment to the:

Traditions of his native Acoli, devoting himself to the study of its indigenous belief system and translation of the oral literature. Even when he wrote his own poetry in English, he tried to stay as close as possible to the forms of his native Acoli, mainly to demonstrate that there were enough resources in his indigenous traditions for his use in the treatment of any topic whatsoever. (Okpewho 1992)

Unlike Achebe and his contemporaries in West Africa who often exploit the oral form in order to Africanize their works, p'Bitek employs the oral tradition and aesthetic to prove its adaptability into contemporary era. For instance in his *Hare and Hornbill*, oral narrative devices such as call and response to engage the audience is used in the tales, repetition of certain words has (derived from the oral narrative) a didactic function. In 'Awili and her Suitors,' there is a repetition of 'the cripple' as in 'the cripple went', 'the cripple returned', 'the cripple woke up.' Repetition is a technique often employed to maintain the attention of the audience. Such oral aesthetics ensure that even when translated into foreign languages, African literary works such as *Hare and Hornbill* can still retain their African identity.

Similarly, the adaptability of oral tradition and aesthetics is depicted in Ngugi's short story "A Mercedes Funeral". Though the story thematically deals with the

issue of classism in postcolonial Kenya, its reliance on African oral aesthetic makes it an authentic African story. In the story, the flexibility of the African oral aesthetic is demonstrated in the narrative style. For instance, in an oral performance, the audience actively participate. In the story, there is an instance where one of the listeners corrected the narrator that Wahinya (the main narrator and protagonist) did not drive a Mercedes when he is alive. This interruption makes the narrator to adjust some details in his story for the benefit of his audience. As Chinwezu et al (1980) assert audience participation in an oral performance can be replicated in the written form-through the use of a narrator who relies on oral devices to encourage audience engagement, Ngugi is able to achieve this where the narrator interrupts the narrative flow to talk to the bartender and his unexpected addresses to listeners and audience. Like p'Bitek, Ngugi in this short story is able to demonstrates that the African oral tradition and aesthetics can be can adapted in order to enhance the modern novel.

Postcolonial Era

Even though most second generation of African writers such as Achebe, p'Bitek and Ngugi, among others transcended into the postcolonial era, the utilization of African oral tradition and aesthetics in contemporary African novel, was rare. This tradition became more prominent among contemporary poets, (Alter-Native Tradition poets such as Niyi Osundare, Odia Ofeimun, Tanure Ojaide, among others). Contemporary African novels became preoccupied with dissecting Africa's postcolonial reality such as political instability, civil wars, class struggle, and genocide, among others. In most cases, writers examine such issues in novels from Marxist, postmodern or realist perspective. Few writers resort to employing African oral tradition and aesthetics in their works for any purpose. When applied, elements of oral tradition are relegated to mere embellishment in the novel. For example, in Nkem Nwankwo's *Danda*, the novelist borrows most of his ideas, narrative, and stories from Igbo culture to create a story about an individualistic man called Danda who is a simple, funny, free-thinker and most importantly, who deviates from convention and tradition of his people.

Igbo oral traditions such as proverbs, belief, names, and songs among others, are used abundantly in the novel to narrate the story of Danda. Despite evidence of such oral elements amplifying the unique nature of the African novel, here, they serve as ornamentations; as tools used to beautify the contemporary novel such as *Danda*. For instance, in the novel names such as 'chi', 'Oja', 'Nsi,' among others, only help the reader in identifying the setting. Again, the 'Kolanut Prayer' in the novel is only an interpretation of Igbo worldview and philosophy and does not in any way help the readers in understanding the character of Danda. Similarly, the use of proverbs in Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie's *Half of a Yellow Sun* does not in any way contribute to character or plot development. This indicates that, similar to the African modernist writers' style of writing, in some contemporary African

novels such as Nwankwo's and Adichie's, even when the oral elements are erased, the storyline, plot or character development will not be affected because the oral elements serve only the purpose of mere ornamentation in the works.

However, though recently, many African writers especially in the diaspora hardly employ African oral tradition and aesthetics in their literary works, a few novelists are able to draw from p'Bitek's idea of adapting the oral tradition and aesthetic to serve present purpose, thus, proving the flexibility of folklore as espoused by Dunes (1965). Despite the influence of globalization, these writers are able to understand that as a cultural product, literature (African) ought to retain some form of essentialism. Their choice to employ the oral tradition and aesthetics in their works proves to critics of African literature/fiction that African oral tradition and aesthetics can still be borrowed to strengthen the modern African novel.

This does not in any way hinder the novel's global outreach. Literary works such as Zakes Mda's *Heart of Redness*, Ngugi's *Wizard of Crow*, 'The Mercedes Funeral', Ojaide's *The Activist*, Kyuka Lilymjok's *The Disappointed Three, Sieged, And Death Finally Died*, and Bivan's *House*, among others, depict that the African oral tradition and aesthetics can be used as a tool by contemporary African writers to enhance their literary works today. For instance, in Lilymjok's *Bivan's House*, proverbs are employed by the author not to serve as mere embellishment but rather to enhance the plot development. In other words, they help the readers comprehend and absorb the political atmosphere and moral decay in Bivan's House (the setting) thereby, adequately shedding more light on African postcolonial reality (the main concern in the novel). One of such examples is demonstrated in the following proverbs:

'The dog is a friend to man because it knows what the hyena will do to it if man is not standing in front of it,' (BH 73).

This proverb means that a vulnerable individual caged in prison has no option but to obey his/her captor. This proverb is made by Yagu about Nicolas; his loyal dog. However, Beckin's plight is reflected in this proverb. As a caged bird in Yagu's prison, she endures his abuse silently due to her lack of courage to stand up to him and the absence of people to help her.

'When a tortoise wants to embark on a senseless journey, whatever you tell him, he will not hear until he has received his foolishness,' (BH 215-16)

Meaning any individual who engages in a futile cause will not heed to advice until it is too late or his mistakes have consumed him. Komau; a once honest man who becomes discouraged from pursuing honesty after an unlawful dismissal, feels Talgon's decision to join Jamini's party (Peoples Liberation Party) so as to rescue

Bivan's House from socio-political and economic decay, is futile and will only leads to regret.

A close analysis of proverbs in the text reveals that, the oral traditions such as proverbs, folktales and oral songs, among others, are not relegated to the role of embellishment. Unlike the proverbs employed by Adichie in her *Half of a Yellow Sun*, in *Bivan's House*, they enhance the plot of the story. This indicates that African oral tradition is fluid, always adapting to changing culture/time.

From the above analysis, the employment of African oral tradition and aesthetics in modern African fiction by African writers, can be categorized in three forms. The first form is translation which is common among the apprentice writers. The essence of directly translating the oral form into European languages by these writers, is an attempt on their part to reach a compromise (African and European literature). That is, in an effort to correct the misinterpretation and translation of African oral tradition and aesthetics done by earlier European explorers and critics such as Burton (1865), these writers directly translated elements of African oral tradition in European languages. This method fails woefully because it rendered their works un-African due to cultural difference. Most of the elements of African oral tradition and aesthetics cannot be directly translated, thus, the works' inability to conform to European literary standards.

The second group of writers represented by Fagunwa and Tutola on the other hand, demonstrate that, literature is a cultural product and not reactionary in nature. These writers draw from the oral reservoir of their people not to prove to Eurocentric critics that an African literature exist, but a genius means of fossilizing the African oral tradition and aesthetics in the written form, thus, creating a crossbreed between the two form (written and oral). This idea of essentialising authentic African fiction is further enhanced by later writers such as Ngugi and p'Bitek, and Kyuka, among others. African oral tradition and aesthetics is adapted to enhance the modern form. Instead of a metaphoric or symbolic usage/function, new subjects and context are employed in order to upgrade the old form. As used in Ngugi's 'The Mercedes Funeral. Adaptation allows the writer to explore modern issues such as class struggle, corruption, injustice, and moral decay, among others, in an alternative voice. That is, instead of relying on Eurocentric literary aesthetics like bildungsroman, the writers adopt African oral tradition and aesthetics to capture the stories. In an era of globalization, the idea of reconceptualizing African oral tradition and aesthetics to capture the present, proves its flexibility and adaptability in an ever shifting culture. African writers like Kyuka have demonstrated that a reconceptualised oral tradition can be a viable tool contemporary African writers can use to discuss/examine African postcolonial reality.

The third group represented by Achebe, Soyinka and subsequently, by Nwankwo and Adichie, among others, exploited elements of oral tradition of their culture for the purpose of embellishing their literary works. Exploitation appears to be selective in nature because it lays more emphasis on material tradition and not aesthetics. In a novel like Achebe's *Things Fall Apart*, even though it is a novel portraying the Igbo precolonial society, the narrative structure does not conform to the structure of any African folktale. The author sprinkled the story with proverbs, (a common oral element in Igbo tradition). Exploitation of oral tradition occurred due a shift in the preoccupation and concern of African writers and interests of their target audience. Though the idea stems from identifying with African culture, due to the emergence of modern societies, writers were expected to carter for these changes, as such in some instances, the oral tradition is slightly altered especially if the writer disagrees with it. Unlike the second group of writers who sought to reconceptualise the oral form, this group believes in a metaphoric and not slavish use of the oral form.

Conclusion

It could be said that from its inception in the early 20th century, modern African fiction has been influenced by African oral tradition and aesthetics. Even though as witnessed in both the colonial and postcolonial periods, African oral tradition and aesthetics is a substratum in the evolution of modern African fiction, its role/function is always in a flux, reflecting politics in a given period. The intellectual capacity, audience, and most importantly, politics of a period influence/inform modern African writers on how to employ the oral tradition to Africanize the written form.

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